

Insights and Impact From Five Cycles of Essential Open Source Software for Science

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Executive Summary

Open source software (OSS) is crucial to advance scientific discovery. In particular, biomedical research increasingly depends on computational analysis, and OSS has become critical to making these methods broadly accessible. Despite a steady increase in demand from the scientific community for usable, scalable, secure, and reliable OSS, funding to support the needs of the communities that create it and maintain it has been limited.

For the past five years, the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative has supported the maintenance, growth, development, and community engagement for critical open source tools that are used globally in the life sciences through its [Essential Open Source Software for Science](#) (EOSS) program. To our knowledge at the time of writing, this program (193 grants with \$51.8 million in funding) represents the largest initiative to meet these needs. Stories and data from this unique grantee community represent one of the best available accounts on the impact of the open source foundations of science, and the urgent need to continue and expand support for them. In this report, we set out to review the impact of the first five cycles of the EOSS program to date from multiple perspectives and a variety of data sources, highlighting the support required to sustain OSS as well as the successes of our community. Questions we addressed and associated key findings include:

1. What Support Does the Scientific Open Source Community Need?

While all scientific open source projects request funding for technical work, mature projects also aim to improve their documentation and community building efforts. Additionally, maintainers of mature projects like those funded by EOSS typically feel

equipped to tackle technical challenges associated with their work, but are interested in additional support to streamline their operations (e.g., project management), develop contributor communities, and ensure project sustainability.

2. What Activities Did the Program Fund?

All funded proposals engaged in activities which yielded technical outputs. A wide variety of non-technical outputs were also enabled by EOSS funding for almost all funded proposals. These include traditional scientific outputs like presentations, manuscripts, data and grant proposals, as well as software outputs in support of community, documentation, and training. Reviewing a broad array of outputs is required to understand how projects measure progress in their work.

Panel members present on Open Science for Science and Society at the CZI Open Science 2024 meeting in Boston, Massachusetts, USA.

3. How Did the Program Impact Funded Software Projects?

EOSS funding is intended to support the maintenance and ongoing development of scientific OSS projects, so the primary area of intended impact is on the software projects themselves. EOSS-supported projects are asked to adopt community guidelines (e.g., Codes of Conduct), encouraging the creation and maintenance of welcoming, inclusive communities. OSS projects supported by EOSS also reported a positive impact of funding on project maintainers through the recruitment of contributor communities and other outcomes that facilitate project sustainability.

4. How Did the Program Impact the Broader Open Source Community?

EOSS-supported software projects are leaders in scientific OSS, representing some of the most widely used and foundational packages for researchers and other software developers. A relatively high proportion of these projects apply software development best practices and continue to implement such practices during the course of their funded work, serving as examples to the rest of the OSS community. In addition to demonstrating best practices, many EOSS grantees engaged in collaborations with other software projects: nearly half of all funded proposals reported collaborative interactions with one or more other open source projects during the period of funding, including some collaborations that arose through CZI events.

5. How Did the Program Impact Diverse Participation in Scientific Open Source?

Improving diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) bolsters the quality of science, but these activities are often deprioritized in under-resourced projects. Open source software was historically led by white men from North America and Europe; to change this trend there must be increased leadership and participation from members of previously underrepresented groups. Although we did not find changes to PI demographics across EOSS cycles, over half of funded projects reported EOSS funding as key to engaging contributors from underrepresented groups, translating documentation to additional human languages, and performing outreach to new demographics and groups.

6. How Did EOSS-Funded Projects Impact Biomedical Research?

All open source projects funded through the EOSS program were deemed “essential” for science and chosen for funding based on their existing adoption and impact, in particular for the biomedical community. Characterizing the impact of EOSS as a whole on biomedical research is a challenging task, but building direct connections between funded outcomes and examples of scientific progress is key to justify investments in open source.

We used several approaches to building connections between projects and scientific progress. EOSS-supported software projects are mentioned and cited extensively in scientific literature, highlighting the large volume of research that relies on these projects. EOSS funding has also improved usability and accessibility of scientific software for all users, as well as users with disabilities, resulting in increased uptake by the research community. Finally, EOSS-funded projects are connected to a wide variety of biomedical advancements—development of new resources for biomedical topics, use of software packages in platforms, and use or implementation of features that enable cutting-edge scientific discovery.

Foreword: Supporting the Computational Foundations of Biology

By Carol Willing

In 1987, I dreamed of using emerging digital communications technology to open access to learning materials so everyone could discover the knowledge needed to solve critical problems facing humanity. I've dedicated my career to this bold dream.

I have been able to work towards this dream through my contributions to Python, Jupyter Notebooks, JupyterHub, and Binder. Python has become the most popular open programming language for working with data, AI, and machine learning. The impact of Jupyter Notebooks has been remarkable, with over 11 million Jupyter notebooks created in a decade. The Jupyter team has revolutionized how science is being taught in our universities, how research is visualized and published, and has facilitated greater collaboration across scientific disciplines.

The technical accomplishments of Python, Jupyter, and the Scientific Python ecosystem are impressive. Yet, people are most vital to a project's success. I have seen firsthand how, unfortunately, the lack of adequate funding for sustaining foundational open-source software often leads to burnout among maintainers, a focus on coding at the expense of usability, low levels of inclusivity, and other challenges. Thankfully, over the last five years, leaders at CZI have stepped in to close these gaps and support the open source ecosystem.

Scaling Possibilities: EOSS

Open-source software goes far beyond writing code for a project. Maintainers create modern building blocks like software, hardware, development tools, infrastructure, CI/CD, cloud computing, processes, mentoring, community management, documentation, and governance.

High-impact open-source developers have scientific domain knowledge as well as deep software experience. They look for opportunities to scale impact while reducing human toil.

In 2019, CZI made a visionary move to establish the Essential Open Source Software for Science grant program and thus, became a leader in open science sustainability, research possibilities, and impact. This program aligned well with CZI's bold mission: investing in technology and research to make it possible to cure, prevent, or manage all disease by the end of the century.

I remember clearly when, at SciPy 2019, the CZI team presented their vision for supporting open-source software for science. They recognized the value of collaboration between CZI and open-source projects, such as scikit-image, napari, and Binder, in evolving imaging tools and foundational projects for reproducible, shareable computing environments. The CZI team set out to solve the challenge that projects often need more investment a few years into development, which is, paradoxically, right when they become widely used. As a project leader, I agree that maintenance, documentation, community management, and leadership have too often been underfunded or left unfunded. The EOSS grant program was groundbreaking in its support of essential open-source tools. The EOSS grants blazed a new trail in open-source funding, sustainability, and project health by supporting the basics, beyond just code. These grants also valued diversity and inclusion in open-source projects by asking proposers to consider their project's efforts to be inclusive.

Sustaining foundational projects requires aligning incentives for enterprises, government, academia, and research organizations. CZI's leadership and support have opened pathways to stronger research collaborations, inclusion, and scaling impact beyond expectations.

Nurturing a Network of Open Collaborators

The qualitative benefits of EOSS may be challenging to measure, but supporting open-source projects reinforces the foundation needed to scale open science. The EOSS program has helped projects:

- Propagate open standards
- Increase knowledge sharing within and across domains
- Adopt best practices for cloud computing, scaling, DevOps, and cybersecurity
- Scale access beyond techies to domain scientists through documentation and computational narratives
- Connect with global contributors

Biomedical research hubs benefit from the cross-pollination of ideas and processes with other open-domain hubs, such as physics, space, climate, and economics. JupyterHub and The Turing Way work to foster inclusive leadership, improve user documentation, and empower domain experts to use best practices when deploying JupyterHub and BinderHubs. By funding many of the core software libraries that enable collaborative research, the EOSS program is paving the way for the same model to gain broader adoption in biomedicine.

Members of the open science community at the CZI Open Science 2024 Meeting in Boston, Massachusetts, USA.

Bringing More People Into the Solution Space

As a 58-year-old woman, I bring a unique perspective to the technical leadership of the Python language and Project Jupyter. Underrepresented individuals are rare as open-source maintainers and very rare in leadership positions.

Projects also funded by CZI such as Data Umbrella, pyOpenSci, rOpenSci, or initiatives like The Turing Way, are working to create healthy, inclusive projects. They offer all contributors training, documentation, workshops, and informal mentoring. Given the complexity of bioscience challenges, embracing diverse viewpoints and interdisciplinary ideas is crucial for surfacing new ideas and pathways to success.

In Conclusion

My dream now includes delivering knowledge via open-source tools to empower collaborative leaders in open science, including software, hardware, processes, data, and infrastructure. Great leaders inspire others to lead, encourage others, and focus on building systems — a helix of technology and humans — that can scale and have a multiplier effect on their ecosystem's success.

As a member of the CZI Open Science Advisory Board, I have witnessed firsthand the impact of the EOSS grant program on the Scientific Python and R ecosystems, both quantitatively and qualitatively. I've also seen the program's impact on research in the Global South, building inclusive research teams and spreading knowledge and best practices worldwide.

I sincerely hope that the results of EOSS's success and CZI will continue to provide visionary leadership in open-source tools for science.

Introduction

Open source software (OSS) is essential to modern scientific research, advancing biomedical discovery while providing reproducibility and transparency. Unlike proprietary or closed software, OSS is free and accessible, allowing anyone to learn from its code base, and ideally reuse and improve it. Biomedical research increasingly depends on computational methods, and OSS has become critical to making these methods broadly available.

Despite the importance of research software, there has been a notable gap in scientific funding available for the maintenance, growth, development, and community engagement of established projects. Funding in early phases of development is sometimes available, when software is typically developed to address specific research questions. A preference to fund software tied to specific research programs makes it much more difficult to find funding beyond the initial release, resulting in a systemic barrier in the scalable usage and application of software to a broader variety of research questions.

For the past five years, CZI's [Essential Open Source Software for Science \(EOSS\) program](#) has supported maintenance, growth, development, and community engagement for critical open source tools that are used globally in the life sciences. The goal is to help make the computational foundations of biomedical research more usable and robust by bridging the gap in support for improving documentation, addressing usability, managing the project, and building

community for open source tools that are critical to science.¹ Beyond funding, we have supported grantees through convenings, workshops, interdisciplinary research collaborations, and partnerships. In addition, we funded initiatives that support the participation, retention, and leadership progression for groups underrepresented in scientific open source as we believe this is key for ensuring scientific discoveries can have maximum global impact.

Members of the open science community reunite at the CZI Open Science 2022 Annual Meeting in Santa Rosa, California, USA.

Meaningfully measuring the impact of research outputs that are not cited in the scientific literature is challenging. Despite its necessity for modern research, scientific OSS has struggled to turn this often invisible impact into a compelling case for large funding initiatives and institutional support. In this report, we, the members of the CZI Open Science Program, set out to evaluate the impact of the EOSS program to date along different dimensions. The purpose of this work is to illustrate some of the many successes of our grantees from a variety of perspectives and metrics. Through sharing these data and stories, we hope to elevate the impact of OSS funding in ways that had not been previously possible, but which we believe are the key to successfully

¹ For more detail on these assumptions, see the [ADORE declaration](#), [Ten simple rules for funding scientific open source software](#), and [Appendix C](#).

advancing research using software. We share these learnings to help other science funders understand the potential impact of funding OSS on their programmatic goals, thereby helping shape new funding strategies. The future of science will continue to be built on OSS, and we hope this report can help guide the funding community to make more dedicated investments in OSS and the communities behind it.

Background

EOSS as a Funding Program

At the time of this report's publication, CZI has executed six cycles of the EOSS program, plus a Diversity & Inclusion supplement (EOSS-D&I), for a total of 193 funded proposals and \$51.8 million awarded. The sixth cycle was carried out in partnership with Wellcome Trust and Kavli Foundation as co-funders. This report covers the first five cycles of the EOSS program, including EOSS-D&I ([Table 1](#)). 1,432 total proposals have been submitted across these cycles. Of those, 161 proposals were funded, with an average funding rate of 10-13% across all cycles. A given proposal may contain 1-5 software projects, and 186 individual software projects were supported across the 161 funded proposals.

The program has funded proposals from OSS projects used in a broad range of disciplines in biomedicine and the life sciences. To support the review process, all proposals were assigned a category based on the nature of the domain or analytical method that is the focus of the software. These categories were used to identify suitable reviewers and inform the breadth and scope of the funded portfolio of projects. Research areas described by categories are either foundational (applicable to any area of research) or domain-specific ([Table 2](#), [Figure 2](#)), with domain-specific proposals comprising two-thirds of all funded proposals across the five cycles. Overall, two categories (Machine Learning and Data Analysis, Data Management and Workflows) had the greatest number of funded proposals in the foundational category, with Imaging proposals being the highest number of a domain-specific research category funded. In addition to these domain and analytical categories, projects funded by EOSS represent two different types of software: projects that are dependencies of other software projects, and end-user projects that are used directly by biomedical researchers.²

² For an analysis of how this distinction manifests in visibility of software, see [Biomedical Open Source Software: Crucial Packages and Hidden Heroes](#).

Overview of the Report

The analyses that follow in this report were executed on a variety of data collected via different mechanisms and throughout the grant life cycle ([Figure 3](#)). For example, we reused data collected during grantmaking and grant administration, and we also collected some data specifically for the purpose of this assessment. A brief overview of data sources (with specific analyses listed in parentheses and further described in [Appendix B](#)) includes:

- **EOSS Applications** ([Application Corpus Analysis](#), [Aggregated Application Data](#)): We used applicant responses from both funded and unfunded applications from cycles 1-5. These data were used to evaluate the activities for which open source projects requested funding, as well as the proportion of projects engaging in software development best practices.
- **Needs Assessment Survey** ([Needs Assessment Survey](#)): PIs and key personnel from EOSS cycles 1-4 were asked in August-November 2021 to indicate their interest in additional training or support from a collection of 19 topics CZI staff identified as relevant to scientific OSS development. Fifty-one total responses representing 36+ software projects were initially used to support development of training opportunities, but have been used in this report to provide further context on what EOSS-funded projects need to succeed.
- **Grant reports** ([Grantee Output Analysis](#)): In early 2024, 265 annual reports (interim and final) from 160 EOSS grants were assessed for the type and impact of outputs produced. Data presented from grant reports includes proportions of EOSS grants with particular outputs and impacts, as well as examples of activities related to specific types of impacts.
- **Grantee Impact Survey** ([Grantee Impact Survey](#)): Designed to assess grantee perception of EOSS impact specifically for this report, a survey of PIs and key personnel from EOSS cycles 1-5 in August 2023 yielded 96 responses from 84+ software projects. We combined examples of impact from this survey with the grant report data for [Grantee Output Analysis](#), and also used quotations from respondents as examples in this report.
- **CZ Software Mentions** ([CZ Software Mentions](#)): These data represent software mentions (formal citations and mentions of software names) in biomedical literature for 186 software projects named in funded EOSS proposals from cycles 1-5. Publications included in the analysis span 2013 to 2022.

The nature of these data do not allow us to comprehensively describe how EOSS as a funding program has changed across cycles, nor does it evaluate the efficacy of EOSS as a whole. These

data do allow us to understand both the needs of the scientific open source ecosystem, as well as the impact of EOSS funding at multiple levels.

The first two sections of this report describe the activities crucial for scientific OSS:

1. What support does the scientific open source community need?
2. What activities did the program fund?

The last four sections describe the implications of these activities at from multiple perspectives:

3. How did the program impact funded software projects?
4. How did the program impact the broader open source community?
5. How did the program impact diverse participation in scientific open source?
6. How did EOSS-funded projects impact biomedical research?

Figure 1. Cumulative number of proposals and funding awarded across EOSS cycles.

Table 1. Number of proposals by funding cycle. ³

Cycle	Date of RFA release	Submitted	Funded proposals (% of submitted)	Total software projects across all proposals	Amount of funding
EOSS-1	Jun 2019	293	32 (11%)	44	\$5 million
EOSS-2	Dec 2019	194	23 (12%)	26	\$3.8 million
EOSS-3	Jun 2020	227	17 (13%)	20	\$3 million
EOSS-4	Mar 2021	350	35 (10%)	68	\$11.1 million
EOSS-5	Mar 2022	343	40 (11%)	98	\$12.5 million
EOSS-6	Aug 2023	662	32 (5%)	73	\$11.5 million
EOSS-D&I	Mar 2021	25	14 (56%)	21	\$4.9 million
Total		2,094	193 (9%)	230	\$51.8 million

³ Total software projects across all cycles is smaller than the sum of total projects each cycle because some software projects have been funded more than once. Numbers for EOSS-6 represent funded proposals and amount of funding from CZI, Wellcome, and Kavli combined.

Table 2. Proportion of proposals funded by category and cycle.⁴

Proposal Category	EOSS-1 (% in cycle)	EOSS-2 (% in cycle)	EOSS-3 (% in cycle)	EOSS-4 (% in cycle)	EOSS-5 (% in cycle)	TOTAL (% across cycles)
Foundational:						52 (35%)
Data Management and Workflows	5 (16%)	3 (13%)	1 (6%)	7 (20%)	5 (12.5%)	21 (14%)
Machine Learning and Data Analysis	5 (16%)	4 (17%)	4 (23.5%)	6 (17%)	2 (5%)	21 (14%)
Visualization	2 (6%)	1 (4%)	2 (12%)	3 (8.6%)	2 (5%)	10 (7%)
Domain-Specific:						95 (65%)
Bioinformatics	3 (9%)	2 (9%)	0 (0%)	2 (6%)	2 (5%)	9 (6%)
Cell Biology	2 (6%)	3 (13%)	2 (12%)	2 (6%)	7 (17.5%)	16 (11%)
Clinical Research	0 (0%)	2 (9%)	2 (12%)	1 (3%)	4 (10%)	9 (6%)
Genomics	7 (22%)	3 (13%)	1 (6%)	4 (11.4%)	1 (2.5%)	16 (11%)
Imaging	5 (16%)	2 (9%)	5 (29%)	7 (20%)	7 (17.5%)	26 (18%)
Infectious Disease	-	-	-	-	4 (10%)	4 (3%)
Neuroscience	1 (3%)	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	2 (6%)	4 (10%)	8 (5%)
Structural Biology	2 (6%)	2 (9%)	0 (0%)	1 (3%)	2 (5%)	7 (5%)
TOTAL (% of cycle)	32 (100%)	23 (100%)	17(100.5%)	35 (100%)	40 (100%)	

⁴ Foundational categories represent applications useful across research areas; Domain-specific categories are designed to address certain areas within biomedical research. Each proposal category is defined in [Table A1](#). Infectious disease was not assigned (included as a category) in cycles 1-4.

Figure 2. Proposals funded by cycle and domain-specific category.⁵

⁵ Categories represent the single best applicable category as assigned by CZI staff and are defined in [Table A1](#). Categories are represented for 147 funded proposals in cycles 1-5 (EOSS-D&I awards are not included because they are already represented by projects in cycles 1-3). Infectious disease was not assigned (included as a category) in cycles 1-4. Numbers represent the total number of proposals in each category across all cycles.

Figure 3. Overview of the EOSS grantee community (squares) and data sources (ovals) used in this report. ⁶

1: What Support Does the Scientific Open Source Community Need?

While all scientific open source projects request funding for technical work, mature projects also aim to improve their documentation and community building efforts. Additionally, maintainers of mature projects like those funded by EOSS typically feel equipped to tackle technical challenges associated with their work, but are interested in additional support to streamline their operations (e.g., project management), develop contributor communities, and ensure project sustainability.

1.1 EOSS Applicant Needs

The large number of proposals received via the first five cycles of EOSS solicitations provides a unique opportunity to learn more about the specific needs of scientific OSS projects. We leveraged submitted proposals to learn more about these needs via the [Application Corpus](#)

⁶ Further information about data sources is available in [Appendix B](#).

[Analysis](#) / [Applicant Needs Identification](#), which trained and applied natural language processing models to identify categories of needs.

The proposals received across five cycles of the EOSS program can be used as a proxy to represent the major needs of the broader scientific open source community. As described in [Table 3](#), these needs can be grouped under the following general categories: technical, documentation, community, and training.

Across EOSS cycles 1-5, all proposals generally requested funding for technical work ([Figure 4](#)). In many cases, proposals surfaced multiple needs across categories, which is indicative of later-stage software projects. Indeed, three-fourths of proposals also requested support for documentation and community work, with proposals requesting training representing a subset of those interested in community work. Unsurprisingly, proposals that had needs beyond only technical were more likely to be funded, which reflects the program’s intention to address the gap in funding for later stage projects.

Table 3. Major categories of EOSS applicant needs.

Need Category	Activity
Technical	Updates to code/software: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing components/plugins, integrations ● Improving features/technical capabilities for end-users ● Structural improvements to the codebase (refactoring/rearchitecting, scalability, unit testing)
Community	Materials or events used to engage users or developers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community meetings and outreach to users ● Code of Conduct (CoC) development or process improvement ● Sprints, hackathons ● Blog posts and other announcements ● Governance, strategy, roadmaps and work with advisors
Documentation	Any written material used as reference for users and/or developers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● User manuals ● Contributor guides ● Project website

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tutorials
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hosting in-person or virtual courses and workshops • Mentoring new contributors to the project

Figure 4. Proportion of unfunded and funded proposals requesting needs by category. ⁷

1.2 Gaps in Capacity For EOSS Grantees

We fund EOSS grants to support work specific to their software projects. However, we also realize that scientific OSS projects share a number of challenges that can't be directly solved by money, and for which additional forms of support could be very useful. In order to identify the top priority needs of our grantee community and inform our capacity-building efforts, we compiled a list of 19 topics relevant to scientific open source development and administered a [Needs Assessment Survey](#) from August to November 2021. Fifty-one respondents, representing

⁷ Data from the [Application Corpus Analysis](#) / [Applicant Needs Identification](#).

36+ software projects supported by EOSS cycles 1-4, indicated their interest in additional training or support on the topic to fill gaps in capacity for their software project ([Figure 5](#)).

More than half of survey respondents (59%) identified Planning for sustainability as an urgently needed gap in their overall capacity ([Figure 5A](#)), making it the most urgent need in our survey. Interestingly, this was identified as a Technical topic but intersects heavily with the two non-technical categories (Community and Documentation); short-answer responses also indicated “sustainability” includes many varied subtopics, from fiscal models to volunteer engagement. Deeper investigation revealed very different ideas about what sustainability means for different projects. Other technical needs were not identified as top-priority, which suggests different EOSS projects might have varying and specific technical demands. While help on these more specific technical topics was not reported as an urgent need, respondents did express in short-answer comments a desire to learn from other members of the EOSS community how to optimize and improve technical elements of their work. Additional high-priority topics included themes from the other two categories, Community and Documentation, and were related to project management, governance, and community-building for both contributors and users ([Figure 5 B and C](#)).

Subsequent comments from the [Grantee Impact Survey](#) we conducted in August 2023 included additional insight into ongoing needs from the grantee community. In particular, the identification of financial sustainability beyond the funding period suggests clarity about specific mechanisms of ensuring ongoing work, and included requests for support obtaining follow-on funding, mentorship, or networking with key partners and organizations. There were also more requests for more collaborative opportunities to interact with other grantees, such as additional in-person meetings or funding to make projects interoperable. Finally, grantees reported a need for additional resources to identify and implement best practices for accessibility, diversity and inclusion, and project management.

Discussion of the ways we have attempted to meet needs voiced by the EOSS grantee community is beyond the scope of this report. Regardless, our attempts to summarize these gaps in capacity provide a valuable source of information about how mature, well-established scientific OSS projects engage in grant-funded work. When combined with our knowledge of what scientific OSS projects request in grant proposals, the data presented in this section establish the challenges faced by such projects—from technical work to community building and beyond.

Figure 5. Proportion of grantees surveyed (n=51) ranking urgency of needs.⁸

A. Technical

⁸ Data from the [Needs Assessment Survey](#).

B. Community

C. Documentation

2: What Activities Did the Program Fund?

All funded proposals engaged in activities which yielded technical outputs. A wide variety of non-technical outputs were also enabled by EOSS funding for almost all funded proposals. These include traditional scientific outputs like presentations, manuscripts, data and grant proposals, as well as software outputs in support of community, documentation, and training. Reviewing a broad array of outputs is required to understand how projects measure progress in their work.

An attendee asks a question at the 2020 EOSS Kickoff Meeting in Berkeley, California, USA.

In the previous section, we sought to understand what the projects need to support ongoing development of scientific OSS. With that understanding in mind, we can now turn our attention to what activities and associated outputs were enabled by the EOSS program. The results presented here were compiled from annual reports collected from grantees during their award period ([Grantee Output Analysis](#)), as well as additional feedback from grantees ([Grantee Impact Survey](#)).

This section summarizes types of outputs from EOSS grants. It is not possible to accurately report on the number of outputs per project, as we did not define consistent approaches for grantees to define outputs in their reports. Instead, we discuss the proportion of projects with outputs belonging to particular categories. Although inconsistencies in grantee reporting may still result in underestimates of the proportions of funded grants engaging in activities, we believe this approach still more accurately reflects the major outputs of grant-funded work. The categories described in this section map to the needs of software projects described in the previous section ([Table 3](#)), but also include additional needs related to traditional scientific deliverables ([Table 4](#)). Of the 161 total grants awarded by EOSS in cycles 1-5, 85 (53%) completed their work and submitted a final report, and an additional 72 (45%) submitted at least one interim report by the time of this publication. We summarize the relevance of technical and non-technical outputs among grants below.

Table 4. Categories of outputs identified from EOSS grants. ⁹

Output Category	Activity
Technical*	Updates to code/software
Community*	Materials or events used to engage users or developers
Documentation*	Any written material used as reference for users and/or developers
Training*	Online or virtual course/workshop, mentorship
Manuscript	Preprint, submitted, or published manuscript
Presentation	Seminar or conference presentation (talk or poster)
Proposal/grant	Submitted proposal and/or awarded grant

⁹ Data from the [Grantee Output Analysis](#).

* The first four categories (Technical, Community, Documentation, Training) represent software outputs and match those in [Table 3](#), other categories are scientific deliverables.

Data

Curated dataset (e.g., for benchmark or testing)

bcbio

High-throughput sequencing analysis toolkit bcbio provides an example of a software project that used funding to optimize and improve technical features of the package.

bcbio used EOSS funding to:

1. Label and triage open issues. This eventually led to resolution and closure of hundreds of bugs, questions, and requests from the user community.
2. Review and curate the code base, including removing dead code, improving testing, and separating out code not part of core functionality. The resulting code was more sustainable and robust, making it easier to maintain.
3. Add support for additional features, enabling the software to complete different types of DNA/RNA analysis.

2.1 Technical Activities

Virtually all proposals requested funding for technical work, and indeed all grants for which we received at least one report ([Grantee Output Analysis](#)) and/or a response to the [Grantee Impact Survey](#) yielded technical outputs (n=160 total grants). This is unsurprising given technical work is required for basic maintenance and development of OSS, and represents the essential work of EOSS-funded teams.

While attempting to summarize technical outputs associated with EOSS projects, we encountered a few specific challenges. First, metrics that are useful to track productivity over time for a single project (e.g., number of pull requests) are not useful to compare among projects, because each project has different norms based on the nature of the work involved. Second, projects may use very different language to discuss similar activities, and this variation is difficult to map to final outputs (e.g., code refactoring and reducing technical debt). These challenges are exacerbated by the nature of the data we had at hand: achievements useful for a software project are difficult to fit into the reporting frameworks for traditional scientific research projects. Given the

ubiquitousness of technical outputs, we do not include these in subsequent summaries and instead focus on non-technical outputs.

2.2 Non-Technical Activities

One of the unique characteristics of EOSS as a funding program is its support of non-technical aspects of software development in project work plans. These activities are particularly critical for mature, widely-adopted software projects, which tend to have a solid technical foundation but require additional work to develop a user community and associated resources. Indeed, we found 64% of funded proposals (103 proposals) produced outputs that improved community, documentation, and training ([Figure 6](#)), matching the proportion of funded proposals requesting support for such activities ([Figure 4](#)) and confirming the importance of such activities for software projects at a relatively advanced stage of development. Examples of each of these areas are detailed below.

Community work includes any communication with the user and/or developer community, hosting events to engage them in development work (e.g., sprints), and activities related to governance (e.g., working with advisory groups, developing or updating roadmaps). Examples of such work include:

- [Open Health Imaging Foundation \(OHIF\) Viewer](#): Developed community support, including publishing a [newsletter](#), updated the project website, and provided weekly office hours with lead developers.
- [Common Workflow Language \(CWL\)](#): Created [Mission and Vision statements](#) via an open community-driven process, which was approved by the CWL Leadership team
- [Nibabel](#): Held seminars on the future of brain imaging formats across packages and fields, building relationships throughout the community and allowing identification and reconciliation of a serious incompatibility that inhibited wider adoption of their package.

“

Raising awareness in the community and getting more users for tools developed in our organization is a must for our long term success. I cannot stress enough that without the CZI funding, we would not have enough bandwidth in the organization to approach this challenge in a systematic and dedicated way. I am sure you won't be surprised to hear that sometimes it's a challenge to convince developers or researchers that there are other things outside of software and science that are needed for open source projects to be successful. **We should be able to make big improvements with just one person working on the issues of outreach and engagement.** I am forever grateful for the opportunity to get that one person and demonstrate the value of community managers, communication officers and other less frequent roles in research OSS projects for long-term success.

— *Community support, [OpenFold](#), Karmen Condic-Jurkic*

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Documentation work includes all improvements to the user docs for the software and associated website, as well as other materials for reference by developers (e.g., contributor guide) and users (e.g., tutorials). Grantees shared the following examples of such work:

- [Bioconda](#): Added visualizations for download counts over all packages and for individual packages to the homepage.
- [VisPy](#): Created a [Developer's Guide](#) to help new contributors understand coding standards, how to contribute, where to ask for help, and that all contributions are welcome.

Training work includes hosting or teaching courses and workshops (in-person or virtual) and mentoring new contributors. Examples of training activities include:

- [Apache Arrow](#): Launched a mentorship program to engage apprentices in project development, encouraging advancement of their technical skills and coaching on how to support an open-source community.
- [Dask](#): Hosted the [Dask life science workshop](#), which included 15 pre-recorded lightning talks, three interactive discussion times accessible across time zones in Europe, Oceania, and the Americas, with asynchronous text chat throughout ([video recordings](#))

“

I view this type of funding as very important to the use and update of my projects in the biomedical research community. The reason for this is that major aspects that affect the adoption of a tool are its ease of installation, the available documentation, and the responsiveness of the developers and maintainers. **Without dedicated funding for software development, maintenance and ecosystem building, it is difficult (if not impossible) to expend critical resources on these tasks that are critical to uptake and adoption, but not, in general, to publishing.**

”

— *Non-technical software support*, [Salmon](#), Rob Patro

In addition to outputs associated with community, documentation, and training, some funded projects also produced outputs more traditionally associated with scientific work, including manuscripts (preprints and peer-reviewed papers), presentations (conferences and workshops), grant proposals (including receiving additional funding), and curated datasets used for benchmarking and testing ([Table 4](#)). Out of 161 funded EOSS grants, 30% (n=49) produced manuscripts and 25% (n=40) reported presentations, which were the two most common types of traditional scientific outputs ([Figure 6](#)). Eighteen grants produced both manuscripts and presentations. Interestingly, some projects reported a high number (i.e., >10) of publications related to their funded work, while others reported high numbers of presentations. This pattern may reflect how software teams from different areas of science place value on various types of outputs.

To explore whether variation in types of outputs reported by grants reflected the subdisciplines to which they belonged, we also compared types of non-technical outputs by the main category assigned to funded grants ([Figure 7](#)). Indeed, the proportion of funded grants reporting different types of outputs differed among grant categories. For example, presentations were the most common scientific output for some categories (e.g., Data Management and Workflows, Machine Learning and Data Analysis, and Visualization), while manuscripts were most common for others (Genomics, Clinical Research, Cell Biology; [Figure 7B](#)). This variation across categories also appeared for software outputs. Community outputs were most frequent for some categories (e.g., Data Management and Workflows, Machine Learning and Data Analysis, Imaging), while Documentation outputs were most common for others (e.g., Bioinformatics, Genomics, Clinical Research; [Figure 7A](#)). Given EOSS reporting templates did not specifically prompt respondents to share data for each of these categories, it is possible that such variation is from differences in what is reported, rather than activities in which projects engage. Regardless, this additional

evidence points toward differences among development teams and the value they place on different types of outputs.

The data presented here underscore the need for a broad array of data when assessing the progress of scientific open source projects. In addition to standard scientific outputs, it is important to understand how mature OSS projects are continuing to advance their projects through technical and non-technical development activities.

Figure 6. Percentage of grants (n=161) reporting software outputs (light red) and scientific deliverables (dark red).¹⁰

¹⁰ Data from the [Grantee Output Analysis](#); categories are defined in [Table 4](#).

Figure 7. Percentage of grants (n=161) reporting different output types by proposal category.¹¹

A. Software outputs

¹¹ Data from the [Grantee Output Analysis](#); categories are defined in [Table 4](#). Categories are ordered by decreasing proportion of grants possessing Community outputs (the most common type of output, as per [Figure 6](#)).

B. Scientific deliverables

3. How Did the Program Impact Funded Software Projects?

EOSS funding is intended to support the maintenance and ongoing development of scientific OSS projects, so the primary area of intended impact is on the software projects themselves. EOSS-supported projects are asked to adopt community guidelines (e.g., Codes of Conduct), encouraging the creation and maintenance of welcoming, inclusive communities. OSS projects supported by EOSS also reported a positive impact of funding on project maintainers through the recruitment of contributor communities and other outcomes that facilitate project sustainability.

Attendees interact during a project showcase during the CZI Open Science 2024 Meeting in Boston, Massachusetts, USA.

The previous sections focus on what scientific open source projects require to advance development of their software, and how EOSS funding has allowed projects to meet these needs. The rest of this report focuses on the broader impact of the program — how EOSS-funded projects benefit from the program, the effect of funded activities on the broader open source ecosystem, who participates in scientific open source, and the bigger picture of the program’s impact on biomedical research. Just as the type of outputs from funded grants varies among projects ([Figure 7](#)), there is variation in the types of grantee-reported data that demonstrate the broader impact of EOSS funding ([Table 5](#)). As we continue exploring the program’s impact through various lenses, it may be useful to reference the myriad ways to quantify and qualify such impact. More importantly, these types of data highlight that a single data source, metric, or perspective is unable to capture the impact of OSS projects.

In this section, we’ll begin to explore the ways in which EOSS funding has impacted the ongoing success of supported projects, as reported by grantees. According to a survey of PIs and key personnel for grants from cycles 1-5 ([Grantee Impact Survey](#)), 95% (n=91) considered the grant

extremely or very important to the success of their open source project. While the positive nature of funding is clear, the specific ways in which software projects benefited from grant funding varies. A comprehensive analysis of all impacts from the program is outside the scope of this report, but we’ve begun to identify longer-term impacts of grant support on funded software projects by examining two aspects of open source development: community guidelines and developers/maintainers.

Table 5. Types of data shared by grantees to quantify and qualify the impact of EOSS grants.¹²

Type of Data	Examples
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Achievement of technical implementation, milestones, releases, versioning ● Number of PRs or issues (created and/or closed) ● Code statistics (e.g., code coverage) ● Performance enhancements (e.g., improvements in efficiency)
Outputs	<p>In addition to traditional scholarly outputs (Table 4):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Altmetric score ● Citations of project (mentions in literature) ● GitHub: number of contributions/contributors, stars, forks ● Number of tutorials and other documentation (time spent generating training materials)
General Usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use by other projects (dependencies), use in platforms, reference in training materials (e.g., ELIXIR) ● Downloads of software per month ● Online apps: time spent looking at graphs, types of graphs created, data used to create graphs, data uploaded
User Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Visitors to website (software documentation, tutorials) ● Users trained ● User forums: number of members, questions asked/answered ● Number of participants at community events ● Demographics (e.g., gender, geographic location) of participants

¹² Data from the [Grantee Output Analysis](#).

Media and Other Recognition	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Blog posts, podcasts, youtube● News articles● Social media: tweets, followers, number of interactions/tags● Career advancement of core team members● Awards (posters, prizes, etc)
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3.1 Community Norms of Behavior

All scientific OSS projects funded by the program are expected to have a Code of Conduct (CoC). This guideline is based on the idea that OSS development is fundamentally a collaborative and social endeavor, and norms of behavior eventually become requisite for the resulting community of open source contributors to continue working together. In open source, these values and norms are collectively codified in a CoC; conventionally, a CoC encourages a software project’s community to be welcoming and supportive of diverse participants.

The expectation of a CoC for EOSS-funded projects has enabled change in associated software communities. While this work may seem trivial compared to other challenges faced by OSS projects, adoption of a CoC can require significant effort and resources, especially at the scale at which some EOSS-funded projects operate where there are hundreds or thousands of contributors. The expectation to adopt a CoC does not always occur seamlessly, and organizing people and expectations to enforce a CoC requires substantial effort. Based on the [Grantee Output Analysis](#), software projects associated with twelve funded grants (8%) adopted a CoC for the first time, or implemented a new version of their CoC as a result of their EOSS award. Given a CoC is a requirement for EOSS-funded projects, this means a majority of projects already had a CoC in place. However, adopting a CoC is insufficient for encouraging a healthy and welcoming community. Seven projects that already had a CoC used the opportunity to develop better practices around socializing and enforcing it. EOSS funding enabled [Bioconductor’s release](#) of their CoC in 11 different human languages.

“

This exercise has been quite illuminating, as we have studied the codes of conduct of many different projects and also dealt with quite a diverse membership of our own development team. Indeed we have had to deal with strong objections from several members of the team who have signaled that they have thought codes of conduct are not necessary and are distractions. **Responding to and dealing with these objections has certainly been educational and has revealed the diversity of feelings on these topics in our own team.** Nonetheless we would like to thank the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative for raising the priority of this issue.

— *Adopting a CoC*

”

3.2 Sustainability

The presence of a CoC is only one, albeit essential, component of an OSS project that has the potential for longevity. As previously discussed, a wide variety of characteristics and practices relate to sustainability for OSS. Another challenge of sustainability for scientific OSS is the ability of a project’s developers/maintainers to continue to invest time, energy, and effort in the long-term. 85% (n=82) of respondents to the [Grantee Impact Survey](#) indicated EOSS funding was extremely or very important for supporting the primary maintainers of the project. The specific reason why EOSS funding supports maintainers and developers of a project varies based on the software project, and depends on factors like the size of the developer community and maturity of the project. The following testimonials highlight how directly supporting developers contribute to a more sustainable project:

- [NetworkX](#): “The focus of the [EOSS-funded] project is on building and extending the community of developers for NetworkX [...] it helped to ensure continued uptake and use into the future by building a developer community.” (Dan Schult)
- [QuPath](#): “Without the EOSS awards, it is difficult to imagine where the project would be. QuPath's use was already growing in 2019, but beyond one small internal grant (soon to end) it lacked any future funding. The EOSS was indispensable for the project to transition away from being wholly reliant on a single person — which was in turn necessary to support the sustained steep increase in use (reflected in the grant report metrics).” (Peter Bankhead)

In addition to supporting maintainers of scientific OSS, EOSS grants also used funding to enable another characteristic of projects that promotes sustainability: high-functioning infrastructure. For example, with EOSS funding:

- [MicroManager](#): Modernized the support infrastructure for their software.
- [Bioconductor Build System](#): Continued a long-term project that included GitHub Actions, containerization, and cloud-native solutions for genomics and human genetics. They also began automated testing of all documentation to ensure public-facing resources are mutually compatible and functional.
- [Nextflow/nf-core](#): Supported the infrastructure that acts as the foundation for the community developed pipelines. Added support for all public cloud infrastructure as execution platforms, ensuring users and organizations relying on any of the major cloud providers can run any pipelines on their cloud of choice.
- [PsychoPy](#): Professionalized tools and bridge a gap until their revenue model was fully developed and sustainable.

Zarr

Zarr is a data format specification for efficiently storing N-dimensional arrays with implementations in several programming languages and an associated ecosystem of tools and integrations. It is currently downloaded on average [10,000 times a day](#).

[Version 3 of the Zarr specification](#) was the first universal format specification enabling **feature parity and interoperability across all major programming languages used in scientific computing that implement the format** (Python, R, C, C++, Julia, Java, JavaScript). CZI funding enabled the creation of the Zarr Implementation Council with representatives of these programming languages as well as the development of the project's first formal governance model, steering council, and voting process for core developers and community members. Adoption and continued usage of a common data format is reliant on both solid technical foundations and investment from the community; the combination of efforts represented in Zarr's activities represent the multifaceted effort required to create a sustainable project.

Given sustainability is an inherently long-term outcome, we cannot yet say with certainty whether and how the momentum currently experienced by EOSS-supported projects will continue into the future. Moreover, depending on the project, the path to sustainability can come in many forms and rely on different key elements. We anticipate that the EOSS program's focus on funding work in scientific OSS that is traditionally under-supported is setting more open source projects on the trajectory for success in the long term.

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‘Normal’ biomedical research projects are done in secret and published by the end. Afterwards, developers graduate and leave, and many of the projects die at that point. Thanks to EOSS, we have an alternative scheme: **We work in the open, turn our project into a community project and thus, it doesn't rely anymore on single individuals or groups. It becomes sustainable.**

— *Sustainability in OSS*, [CLIJ](#), Robert Haase

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4: How Did the Program Impact the Broader Open Source Community?

EOSS-supported software projects are leaders in scientific OSS, representing some of the most widely used and foundational packages for researchers and other software developers. A relatively high proportion of these projects apply software development best practices and continue to implement such practices during the course of their funded work, serving as examples to the rest of the OSS community. In addition to adoption of best practices, many EOSS grantees engaged in collaborations with other software projects: nearly half of all funded proposals reported collaborative interactions with one or more other open source projects during the period of funding, including some collaborations that arose through CZI events.

While much of the immediate impact of EOSS funding is experienced by individual projects, one of the goals of the program is to influence positive change across the entire scientific open source ecosystem by promoting knowledge sharing, collaboration and the adoption of best practices. This section begins to describe how the program influenced the overall trajectory and trends of scientific OSS, focusing on software development practices and collaborations among OSS projects.

4.1 Software Development Practices

The founders, developers, and maintainers of scientific open source projects form a heterogeneous population with a broad range of expertise — some are biologists by training who learned to code via necessity to advance their research, while others are trained software engineers with years of expertise in multiple programming languages. Similarly, scientific open source projects represent wide variation in adoption of best practices in software development. Many of these practices are determined by programming language, but there are a core set of practices that indicate a robust, well-thought out software project.

EOSS applications included a set of questions to evaluate the extent to which a proposed project had implemented these practices ([Table 6](#)). To understand uptake of these approaches, we compared the proportion of projects that reported adoption of each practice that were funded to the pool of unfunded applicants ([Aggregated Application Data / Software Development Practices, Figure 8](#)). For two of the eight practices studied, unfunded versus funded applicants either demonstrated similar uptake (issue tracker use) or unfunded applicants were more likely to demonstrate the practice (example code¹³). For the remaining six practices, funded proposals have more often adopted the tool or resource than unfunded proposals.

High uptake of best practices in software development by EOSS-funded projects is not surprising; these projects have wide user adoption and are relatively mature, which means they have most likely needed to adopt these practices to maintain scalability during their maturation. Moreover, they frequently request support to improve their technical infrastructure ([Section 2.1](#)) and community/documentation support ([Section 2.2](#)), continuing to increase their application of best practices. Ultimately, EOSS projects represent a certain caliber and level of excellence in scientific open source, and their use of best practices in software development can serve as an example to the rest of the scientific open source community about how long-term success can happen.

¹³ We attribute the pattern for example code to overrepresentation of researcher-facing software in unfunded projects, which by definition require code examples for users.

Table 6. Software development practices and questions from EOSS applications.

Practice names match those found in [Figure 8](#).

Practice	Application question
Examples/Demos	Are there examples or demo notebooks, scripts, and datasets?
Package Manager	Is there a corresponding package available in a package manager (PyPi, CRAN, etc.)?
Contributor Guide	Does the project have contribution / coding guidelines?
Code of Conduct	Does the project have a code of conduct?
Community Forum	Does the project have a community engagement / Q&A forum (self-hosted, on Stack Exchange etc.)?
CI/Testing	Does the project support continuous integration for testing?
End-User Documentation	Does the project have end-user documentation?
Issue Tracker	Does the project have an issue tracker?

Figure 8. Proportion of software development practices reported for unfunded vs funded proposals across all cycles.¹⁴

4.2 Collaboration Between Projects

Software projects supported by EOSS grants acting as examples of mature and robust software development practices is an important, albeit passive, type of impact. The nature of OSS, however, means that projects directly interact with each other for a variety of reasons. In lieu of a formal assessment of upstream and downstream dependencies for each software project, we’ve instead relied on the descriptions of such collaborations provided by EOSS grantees to characterize their impact. The [Grantee Output Analysis](#) found 54 grants (34% of all funded proposals) reported collaborative interactions with one or more other open source projects during the period of funding. Although EOSS has funded proposals which support more than one software project, the collaborations described here refer to interactions which arose during the funded period. At least some of these collaborations arose due to interactions among grantees during CZI convenings, while many happened naturally from grant-funded activities like developing new features, supporting interoperability, or implementing a new approach. The nature of such collaborative interactions varied, but can generally be described by three separate models:

1. Outreach: Projects with outreach/service to other projects

¹⁴ Each pair of bars represents the proportion of applications in which the primary project (e.g., first listed in application) has incorporated the specific practice or resource. Data from [Aggregated Application Data / Software Development Practices](#).

2. **Linked:** Closely connected projects operating in the same scientific or technical domain and/or within the same umbrella project
3. **Casual:** Short-term interactions, often to create or improve a feature (e.g., by incorporating a new data format)

There are many different examples of these three models of collaboration in EOSS-funded projects, with a few illustrative projects in [Figure 9. Read the Docs](#), for example, engaged over 50 scientific software projects to resolve implementation questions when building, hosting, and sharing their software documentation, demonstrating outreach interactions ([Figure 9A](#), only EOSS projects shown). [Bokeh](#) ([Figure 9B](#)) engaged with multiple other projects belonging to the [HoloViz](#) collection of tools for applying Python plotting packages (linked interactions). The Bokeh grant also planned for integrations with a variety of other scientific open source projects to improve features in Bokeh (casual interactions). Finally, EOSS funded a collaborative grant to support [limma](#), [edgeR](#), and [Glimma](#), a group of [Bioconductor](#) packages for differential analysis of genomic data (linked interactions). This funded grant also worked with [Seurat](#), another EOSS-funded project for single cell genomics, to integrate functionality ([Figure 9C](#)). The EOSS-funded project [Monocle](#) also initiated a collaboration with Seurat during their funding period.

Funding provides the resources for collaboration and, in some cases, the space and time for project leaders to meet and discuss how their software can mutually support others. Collaboration among open source projects can have a wide range of impact on the projects involved; for example, improving interoperability among software projects can facilitate uptake and use of both projects, and collaborating on common technical challenges reduces duplication of effort. These collaborations, of course, move more smoothly when each software project includes tools and resources representing best practices in software development. All of these factors can lead to improved sustainability of open source projects.

[DeepLabCut](#) and [NumPy](#)

NumPy, the fundamental package for scientific computing in Python, highlighted a [case study](#) on their website where fellow EOSS grantee DeepLabCut **cited some of NumPy's features as critical for their tool**. DeepLabCut, a toolbox used to identify features of animals and their movements from video frames, allows researchers to measure and track posture of animals in diverse settings and inform research areas from biomechanics to neuroscience. The features of NumPy that DeepLabCut identified as

critical to ongoing use and development of their tool include:

1. **Numerical analysis:** Image analysis software represents images as arrays of numbers that can be compared across frames. NumPy provides capacity for such array manipulation, providing the foundation for addressing research questions.
2. **Speed:** Processing animal behavior videos using deep learning is computationally intensive, and slow analyses are not only inefficient but potentially contribute to problems with accuracy. NumPy allows handling the amount of data required efficiently and easily for the researcher.

Figure 9. Examples of collaborative relationships among EOSS-supported projects (blue) and other OSS projects (gray).¹⁵

A. Outreach to other projects

¹⁵ Projects in dark-colored boxes represent those reporting the interactions via the [Grantee Output Analysis](#).

B. Linked and casual interactions among projects

C. Linked and casual interactions with a collaborative EOSS grant

5. How Did the Program Impact Diverse Participation in Scientific Open Source?

Improving diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) bolsters the quality of science, but these activities are often deprioritized in under-resourced projects. Open source software was historically led by white men from North America and Europe; to change this trend there must be increased leadership and participation from members of previously underrepresented groups. Although we did not find changes to PI demographics across EOSS cycles, over half of funded projects reported EOSS funding as key to engaging contributors from underrepresented groups, translating documentation to additional human languages, and performing outreach to new demographics and groups.

The previous section discussed how EOSS funding affected individual software projects. We turn our attention in this section to a specific type of ecosystem-level impact: the diversity of individuals who participate in open source as leaders, developers, and users. CZI's work in science aims to build a more inclusive, just, and healthy future for everyone, a necessary part of which is [addressing who does research, what questions are asked, who participates, and who has access](#). Representative science is key to making that a reality because it creates opportunities for discoveries that may otherwise be missed, and ensures that all discoveries can benefit everyone.

The EOSS program has recognized the importance of DEI in open source by advertising the calls for proposals widely, requiring a statement on DEI for each submitted proposal, and providing funding specifically to support developers of OSS to reduce financial barriers to participation. In this section, we specifically explore the impact of EOSS funding on diverse leadership and participation in scientific open source projects.

5.1 Principal Investigator Diversity

Historically, open source development happens via globally-distributed communities. Since participants are able to remain anonymous, understanding community demographics can be challenging. However, CZI collects data about the demographics of applicants (i.e., PIs) to competitive RFAs like EOSS. Such data are not used in final funding decisions, but they do provide a useful way to understand retrospectively how EOSS leadership compares to the general open source community ([Aggregated Application Data](#) / [PI Demographics](#)).

At present, OSS development is [predominantly led by white men](#) from North America and Europe. This bias is perpetuated into other roles: most maintainers and contributors match that

demographic, which tends to attract users that are similar to them as well. In the context of equity, this makes sense — these demographics are most likely to have the privilege of committing volunteer time to under-resourced open source projects.

We found that leaders of EOSS grants recapitulate the same pattern found across open source projects in general, where the majority of funded PIs were white men ([Figures 10A and B](#)) from organizations in North America and Europe ([Figure 10C](#)). This consistency is perhaps unsurprising. EOSS-supported software projects tend to be mature and well-established, with the original white, male founders continuing to serve as leaders of projects. New projects take time to develop and mature, meaning the baseline demographics are very slow to change. There has been a general increase in funded applicants choosing not to respond to questions about PI race/ethnicity and gender, confounding efforts to understand the demographics of PIs in the EOSS grantee community.

Figure 10. Demographics of PIs for funded EOSS grants across cycles. ¹⁶

A. Race/ethnicity

¹⁶ Additional descriptions of data are available in [Aggregated Application Data / PI Demographics](#). A) Equivalent race/ethnicity data are not available for EOSS cycles 1-3; categories with low numbers of responses were collapsed to a single category to preserve privacy of respondents, following CZI data sharing guidelines. B) Women, non-binary, and third gender are collapsed to a single category of underrepresented genders. C) PI locations were assigned a region using classification from the [World Bank](#). Data represents location of PI affiliate organization for EOSS-1 and PI country of origin for EOSS 2-5.

B. Gender

C. Geographic location

5.2 Diverse Participation in EOSS-Funded Projects

While the pool of funded PIs does not reflect the diversity of the global population engaged in open source development, EOSS efforts to support DEI in OSS has influenced who is able to

engage with supported software communities and the contributor and user level. According to the [Grantee Output Analysis](#), 96 funded proposals (60%) reported positive results in their work to enhance diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) in their projects. Further, 59% of respondents (n=57) from the [Grantee Impact Survey](#) said EOSS funding was very or extremely important for supporting efforts to improve diversity and inclusion in their funded software projects. Unsurprisingly, all 14 funded D&I proposals reported outputs that related to DEI in open source. In addition to adopting and enforcing codes of conduct ([Section 3.1](#)), examples of DEI outputs include engaging contributors from underrepresented groups, translating documentation to additional human languages, and performing outreach to new demographics and groups ([Table 7](#)).

Contributors from underrepresented groups: 37% of funded EOSS grants (n=60) reported activities during their funded work that helped support engagement of new contributors from groups previously underrepresented in their projects. In some cases, these were efforts to make the contributor experience generally more inclusive, while other projects supported new contributors with mentorship or internships. Examples of these efforts include:

- [The Galaxy Project](#): Supported maintainers in areas (e.g., Sri Lanka, Australia) that were previously difficult to fund.
- [NumPy](#): Organized and participated in sprints aimed at individuals underrepresented in open source, such as Women in Machine Learning and Data Science Berlin (May 2021), SciPy India (September 2021), and PyData Global (October 2021). Expanded their active maintainer group by 60% (including its first female maintainer), and gained first-time code contributors from Africa, Asia, and South America.
- [NetworkX](#): Mentored Outreachy and Google Summer of Code interns, including women from low-income countries who have continued to engage with the project after the end of the internship.

“

Until recently, contributing to open source was mostly limited to those who had time to volunteer, as well as the ability to take risks in their career. CZI EOSS has transformed that by **allowing people to contribute who could normally ill-afford to do so.**

— *Diverse contributors, [scikit-image](#), Juan Nuñez-Iglesias*

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Translation to additional human languages: Virtually all scientific OSS has supporting documentation and the user interface written in English, and few resources exist to support users

in other human languages. 7% of funded projects (n=12) reported activities translating software documentation or community resources into human languages besides English; Spanish, Portuguese, and French were the most common. This is a higher level of impact than expected from the handful of projects initially proposing to engage in human language translation. Examples of such work include:

- [nf-core: Recorded](#) videos for foundational training in 5 languages.
- [PsychoPy](#): Provided [documentation](#) and [workshop materials](#) for translating their software to other human languages
- [NumPy](#): launch their first package translations (Arabic and Portuguese).

Outreach to new demographics and groups: Specific demographics of individuals that projects engaged varied depending on the existing software user communities; these activities included outreach to a wide range of groups including (but not limited to) women, BIPOC (Black, Indigenous, and people of color), and researchers from low and middle income countries (LMICs). 25% of funded projects (n=41) reported activities that made EOSS-supported software and associated materials (e.g., documentation and training content) more accessible to new demographics of researchers. Examples include:

- [QIIME 2](#): Partially funded an online workshop taught by 22 instructors across 4 continents that reached 75 participants from at least 25 different countries on 6 continents. Thousands more participants tuned in live to view, with the recording continuing to receive thousands of views. Learnings from this workshop are detailed in [this paper](#).
- [nf-core](#): Hired Developer Advocates to focus on underrepresented regions, start a mentorship program for users in regions with little or no local bioinformatics support, and fund online training and hackathons for accessible involvement, with a notable increase in the number of community members joining from goal regions such as Latin America and Africa. This project credits the extent of their DEI program to EOSS funding.

Open source communities include everyone who interacts with the software—leaders, contributors, and users. Efforts to support diverse participation at each of these levels is a valid way to make a project more equitable and diverse. In fact, some projects have succeeded in building more diverse teams of contributors by first building a more representative user community; moreover, the engagement of diverse contributors from underrepresented groups may eventually promote more equitable representation at the leadership level as well. Many different approaches are required, and collectively, EOSS-supported projects are demonstrating an impressive record of engaging a global and diverse community of researchers and

programmers. Systemic biases in the sciences have a long history that will not be corrected overnight, but these data show that funding models that prioritize DEI can accelerate much-needed progress.

“

DEI is something that most of us agree is important. The problem is that anything that isn't the TOP most urgent issue is likely to get sidelined in a busy team. **CZI funding meant that we could hire someone with DEI as the key component to their job which means it doesn't get forgotten.** That means making sure we could run new-contributor workshops, team-building code-sprints, translator training, a new blog site all with the aims of improving our DEI. Without dedicated staff these would have been seen as ‘great to do when we have time’ and would not have been achieved.

— *Prioritizing DEI*, [PsychoPy](#), Jonathan Peirce

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3D Slicer

Visualization and image analysis software 3D Slicer engaged in an extensive effort to support internationalization and improve global access to their analysis tools, resulting in more diverse, equitable, and inclusive developer and user opportunities. Evidence of this work:

1. **Language support:** Creation of the [3D Slicer in My Language](#) subproject allowed translation of documentation to 45 languages and supported involvement of individuals in 30 countries.
2. **Downloads:** There has been an increase in the number of downloads from non-English speaking African and Latin American communities. During the first and second years of funding, downloads in Senegal and Mauritania increased by 72% and 204%, respectively.
3. **Contributors:** Prior to CZI funding, there were no 3D Slicer developer groups in Africa and Latin America; now there are active groups including female engineers and students in Senegal, Mexico and Brazil.

Table 7. Categories of impact on DEI for EOSS projects.¹⁷

DEI Category	Example Activities
Contributors from underrepresented groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engaging individuals that diversify the experiences of a core team ● Mentoring interns from programs like Outreachy ● Creating materials for contributors that explicitly support inclusiveness
Translation to additional human languages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Translating existing documentation or tutorials into human languages besides English ● Giving talks or workshops in languages other than English
Outreach to new demographics and groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Giving presentations to targeted professional societies (e.g., Women in Data Science) ● Holding coding sprints or hackathons with targeted groups (e.g., PyLadies) ● Holding workshops in underserved locations in the world ● Outreach to minority serving institutions (MSIs)

¹⁷ Synthesized from [Grantee Output Analysis](#).

6: How Did EOSS-Funded Projects Impact Biomedical Research?

All open source projects funded through the EOSS program were deemed “essential” for science and chosen for funding based on their existing adoption and impact, in particular for the biomedical community. Characterizing the impact of EOSS as a whole on biomedical research is a challenging task, but building direct connections between funded outcomes and examples of scientific progress is key to justify investments in open source. We used several approaches to building connections between projects and scientific progress. EOSS-supported software projects are mentioned and cited extensively in scientific literature, highlighting the large volume of research that relies on these projects. EOSS funding has also improved usability and accessibility of scientific software for all users, as well as users with disabilities, resulting in increased uptake by the research community. Finally, EOSS-funded projects are connected to a wide variety of biomedical advancements — development of new resources for biomedical topics, use of software packages in platforms, and use or implementation of features that enable cutting-edge scientific discovery.

According to the [Grantee Impact Survey](#), 74% (n=71) of respondents said EOSS funding was extremely or very important to the uptake and use of their project in the biomedical research community. In this section, we examine the impact of EOSS funding on biomedical research from three perspectives—use of EOSS-supported projects as documented in scientific literature, improvements to usability and accessibility, and engagement of EOSS-funded software in specific biomedical research areas.

6.1 Mentions of Software in Scientific Literature

Given that scientific OSS is foundational for modern biomedical research, it should be possible to assess its impact using standard metrics of scientific achievement, namely citations in scientific literature. However, writing formal manuscripts is not always a priority for developers of scientific software ([Figure 7](#)), and sometimes a recommended citation format for scientific software is not available in the absence of a paper describing the project. Additionally, researchers rarely cite all software used in an analysis, even if such citation information is available. As a result, formal citations are not necessarily a useful source of data to assess software impact in science.

To address this challenge, we relied on the [CZ Software Mentions](#) dataset to supplement our understanding of the use of OSS in scientific literature. This dataset was developed by mining the full text of a large number of scientific articles enriched for biomedical literature, including the NIH PubMed Central collection, for informal mentions of scientific software. Given the nature of

the data processing, this dataset should include formal citations as well as informal mentions, with the results reported here representing the number of scientific papers published per year that used a particular piece of software.

We extracted mentions data for 186 software projects supported by the 161 EOSS grants awarded in cycles 1-5. In total, EOSS projects were mentioned in 774,050 scientific papers in a time period spanning 2013-2022.¹⁸ 619,715 of those papers were published between 2019 and 2022, corresponding with the five EOSS cycles. While these mentions are not necessarily the direct result of EOSS funding, they validate that software supported by the EOSS program represents some of the most crucial and widely-used scientific open source projects currently in development, suggesting that funding these projects can support and enable a large volume of published research. In many cases, software mentions continued to climb very rapidly during and after the grant period. The high proportion of biomedical literature represented in the collection of literature analyzed allows us to relate this to the program's impact on biomedical research in particular.

The software projects with the highest number of mentions in the period considered ([Figure 11A](#)) include projects from a variety of project categories ([Table A2](#)) — Imaging, Neuroscience, Cell Biology, Bioinformatics, Visualization, Genomics, Machine Learning and Data Analysis, Infectious Disease. Given the limitations of software citation metrics as described above, the number of mentions better encapsulates the reach of these software projects than traditional citations. For example, one of the projects displayed in [Figure 11A](#), [DESeq2](#), has been mentioned in 45,154 papers in the dataset. There is a [recommended scientific manuscript to cite](#) for DESeq2, which to date has only [~37,000 citations](#) total. Note that the number of research projects and scientific results relying on this highly-cited software surpasses even what is considered to be highly cited work in scientific literature. In addition, there were many EOSS software projects whose impact has yet to be fully realized, as indicated by their rapid growth rate in recent years ([Figure 11B](#)).

Although the data on software mentions provides important context and is in many ways an improvement on standard citation data, they must be interpreted carefully. A lack of citations or mentions does not mean the software was nonexistent or not being used, and we must assume we are still underestimating the number of publications that used EOSS-supported software. In some cases, this is an issue with the data pipeline used to process the names of software and associated data; in other cases, this may be because the name of the software is a new enough addition to an existing collection of tools that it has not yet emerged into scientific literature. Moreover, not all projects have the same visibility and importance to the researchers writing the

¹⁸ Data represent the years 2013 as a baseline and 2016-2022 representing time prior to and after the start of EOSS in 2019.

papers. For example, researchers are more likely to have interacted directly with (and thus cite) a program like [GATK](#) (Genome Analysis Toolkit), as compared to [pip](#) (a tool for installing Python packages). Additional data should be assessed as a part of identifying the impact of scientific software, particularly for software libraries that act as infrastructure or dependencies for researcher-facing ones.

Figure 11. Top ten EOSS software projects based on mentions in publications.¹⁹

A. Total number of papers

¹⁹ Number of mentions per year, based on [CZ Software Mentions](#).

B. Growth rate from 2019-2022

6.2 Usability and Accessibility

Traditional metrics for scientific research, like mentions in literature, differ from those used for software improvement. Success for a software project focuses more on the number of users and engagement with the associated community. In this section, we'll explore the successes of EOSS-funded projects in expanding their user communities through usability and accessibility improvements.

As with software mentions, this evidence is not necessarily restricted to biomedical research, but can still be used to understand the impact of the EOSS program on biomedicine. EOSS-funded projects include software that many biomedical users might not even recognize as essential to their work, but nevertheless, represent a cornerstone to modern biomedical research. Some projects are foundational ([Table A2](#)) in that they are used across scientific domains (e.g., [Matplotlib](#)), and some projects are used primarily by other software packages (e.g., [funson](#)). Funding such projects supports all users of the software, including biomedical researchers. The metrics used to track these improvements document general patterns in software use, agnostic to the specific research interests of the users. Many software projects supported by the EOSS program report impressive gains in the number of users during their award period, including the following examples:

- [PsychoPy](#): Experienced a doubling of their monthly active users, from 20,000 at the start of funding to nearly 40,000, with growth attributed to EOSS funding.
- [PyMC3](#), [ArviZ](#), and [CmdStanPy](#) (interface to [Stan](#)): Designated as critical by PyPi on July 8, 2022 because they were in the top 1% most downloaded projects in the previous six months.

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The CZI funding has allowed us to have a real focus on ease of use, and accessibility. This opens up the software, and therefore the scientific methods for which it is used to less represented, and less funded researchers.

— *Software useability, [BrainGlobe Atlas](#), Adam Tyson*

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Accessibility of the user interface is a type of software improvement that supports the experience of all users. Creating software that is accessible for users with disabilities — for example those who are Blind, Deaf and hard of hearing — requires intentionality, but this effort is generally not considered a top priority for OSS projects. The [CDC](#) estimates that 1 in 4 (27%) of adults in the US have some type of disability, meaning that for every million OSS users, we may be excluding up to about 200,000 potential participants. Individuals with disabilities have historically been, and continue to be, largely excluded from scientific open source development and use, despite the fact that improvements that make software accessible to them can also directly support other members of the community, like those whose first language is not English. EOSS funding helped projects engage in accessibility work, for example:

- [UpSet](#) received funding to make data visualizations accessible; EOSS funding allowed them to work with a blind and low-vision population as a part of their grant’s goals.
- [Bokeh](#) focused all documentation work on reducing text complexity and improving readability for dyslexic users and contributors, and included accommodating assistive technologies in their roadmap thanks to EOSS funding.

Jupyter

Jupyter represents an ecosystem of open source tools that enable researchers to work with code and data in a single interface. The project has been downloaded over 64M times (and it is currently estimated that on any given day 5,000 sessions are active, or over 1.5M sessions a year). EOSS funded the **creation of an official Jupyter accessibility subproject**. The accessibility team eliminated the hundreds of accessibility warnings and errors in the text editor underlying the Jupyter Notebook identified through an automated accessibility auditing suite. They also released a public accessibility roadmap for JupyterLab, an official JupyterLab accessibility statement, and completed a first series of [accessibility workshops](#) comprising presentations, discussions with accessibility experts, and follow-up sprints to add alt-text descriptions to JupyterLab’s documentation. Not only is this grant supporting accessibility improvements for a major scientific computing platform, but they are making information about their methods and approach available for other scientific open source projects to emulate.

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Accessibility work is massively underfunded in tech, even more so in open source and scientific computing. Not to mention that accessibility related work is often seen as a ‘nice to have’ or ‘add on’ rather than a priority and foundational work needed to achieve the goals of open source, open research, and open education. A great part of the web and the majority of the open source tools for scientific computing are inaccessible to people with disabilities who are effectively excluded from our communities. Without this grant there is no way we could have made some progress towards making JupyterLab more accessible. There is still a lot to do (years of neglect and debt) but we are in a better place than [...] before the grant.

— *Software accessibility, [Jupyter](#), Tania Allard*

”

Panel members present on AI in Open Research at the CZI Open Science 2024 meeting in Boston, Massachusetts, USA.

6.3 Use of EOSS-Funded Software in Biomedical Research

Previously in this section, we established the usefulness and limitations of using traditional measures of scientific research (e.g., citations in literature) and software (e.g., number of users) to understand the impact of software on scientific research. In this section, we'll explore connections between EOSS-funded projects and usage in biomedical research tools and publications.

To understand how the EOSS program affects subdisciplines across biomedicine, we will again reference the categories used to identify the type of domain a particular grant represents, with our previous discussion assigning one category to each proposal ([Table A2](#)). In addition to assessing grantee needs ([Section 1](#)), the [Application Corpus Analysis](#) modeled each scientific domain separately and identified which proposals fell into a given category, with potentially more than one category assigned to each proposal. We then compared these assignments with categories manually curated by CZI staff). The automated categorization approach resulted in a more comprehensive picture of the impact of EOSS projects across biomedical subdisciplines

([Figure 12](#)), and suggests manual curation underestimates impact of each software project across biomedicine. For example, the manual curation approach indicated only 6% of funded EOSS proposals include software for bioinformatics ([Figure 4](#)). According to the automated categorization, however, 56% of funded projects are relevant to the field of bioinformatics. Ultimately, this shows that the impact of scientific software is multi-dimensional, and not limited to the main category to which a proposal is initially designated or assigned.

Second, a number of projects with a broad research audience reported that the EOSS program allowed them to expand their software to support biomedical research:

- [scikit-image](#): Used EOSS funding to improve library documentation in relation to biomedical data analysis, making it easier for new users to learn about it. They also prioritized development of new features with important biomedical use cases (e.g., Thin Plate Spline warping and voxel spacing in region properties).
- [QIIME 2](#): Expanded tutorials into new biomedically-relevant domains, such as pathogen genomics and identification.
- [ETE Toolkit](#): Introduced features to support human microbiome studies, such as phylogenetic profiling, comparisons among samples, and other related analyses.
- [SymPy](#): Worked on code to support biomechanical musculoskeletal modeling.
- [Orange Data Mining](#): Supported the growing size of datasets in biomedical research by expanding the capability of their software to accommodate very large datasets using disk-based approaches.
- [Bokeh](#): Working towards adapting and enhancing their software for biomedical applications, such as including functionalities like gridded image and time series visualizations for large data in the browser.
- [Spyder](#): Adding remote development features to enable biomedical users to manage data and compute-intensive programming tasks in HPC clusters or cloud providers from the ease and efficiency of their local development environments.

The examples above highlight specific improvements to software features and capabilities to provide biomedical researchers more robust and efficient analyses. Other projects focused on creating resources that can be reused by researchers, which can enable reproducibility:

- [ITK-SNAP](#): Deployed new medical image analysis pipelines, which are freely available to the public and documented online.

- [nf-core](#): Built a resource where the community can collect and curate tooling and pipelines, which are essential for a great deal of work across biomedicine.

In addition to reuse by individual researchers, EOSS-funded projects have created tools or resources that are being used by other software or platforms to advance biomedical research. Examples provided by current projects include:

- [MicrobiomeDB](#): Developed data analysis apps and advance functionality of their analysis platform; two such apps are planned for use in two other projects: [VEuPathDB](#) (Eukaryotic Pathogen, Vector and Host Informatics Resource) and [ClinEpiDB](#) (for clinical and epidemiological data).
- [seqr](#): Adopted as a key component of the existing NIH-NHGRI Genomic Analysis, Visualization and Informatics Lab-space ([AnVIL](#)) cloud platform.
- [3D Slicer](#): Used by the MONAI (Medical Open Network for Artificial Intelligence) Label platform and has been widely adopted for medical image segmentation. This approach was recommended in the 2022 GPU Technology Conference [keynote address](#) by NVIDIA CEO Jensen Huang.

The final way to assess the impact of EOSS funding on biomedicine is by pinpointing specific high-impact scientific outcomes for biomedicine. These contributions represent innovation in biomedical research, with specific contributions to transforming how science is done:

- [DESeq2](#): Developed a new type of statistical analysis for genomic data in Bioconductor (generation of null hypothesis for genomic ranges). They also collaborated with other projects to develop a "tidy framework" for genomic data, which continues to be actively developed and shared as an emerging tool in the community.
- [dynamo](#): Along with related tools in the Aristotle ecosystem, made critical contributions to the emerging analytical realm of time and spatially-resolved single cell genomics datasets.
- [SciPy](#), [NumPy](#), [scikit-learn](#), [Matplotlib](#), [pandas](#), [OpenMM](#): Were explicitly cited as software used in a highly cited paper [Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold](#) (Nature 2021).
- [IQ-TREE](#): Dramatically improved its speed and scalability, addressing a major computational bottleneck and enabling rapid COVID-19 analysis as datasets got updated with thousands of new genomes per day at the peak of the pandemic in 2020.

Seurat

Seurat is an R package designed for analysis of single-cell RNA-seq data. As of June 2024, Seurat is downloaded more than 40,000 times a month (over 2M downloads since its initial release), and monthly downloads have more than doubled since CZI support began. Specific biomedical advancements enabled by Seurat include:

1. Expansion to **support a wide variety of spatially resolved data types**, which promises to redefine our understanding of cellular interactions and the organization of human tissues.
2. Introduction of **scalable computational infrastructure** that enables the analysis and exploration of millions (and eventually billions) of cells, even on a personal computer (see [Hao et al bioRxiv, 2022](#)).
3. Launching a web application that enables users to **rapidly map their own single-cell datasets onto a larger curated reference dataset**, including a widely used peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC), with the first release of the web application garnering over 6,000 unique user sessions collectively mapping over 30 million cells.

Although publications and citations are a traditional marker of impact in research, and relatively easy to assess, scientific software influences biomedical research in much more far-reaching ways that can be difficult to identify and quantify. We've identified evidence of EOSS impact on the larger biomedical research ecosystem in three areas: references to funded software projects in scientific literature, usability and accessibility of EOSS-funded projects, and use of EOSS software projects by researchers and platforms to advance knowledge in biomedicine. In documenting these perspectives on impact, we underscore a broader need to [map the diverse outputs](#) produced by scientific software to measure impact beyond that which is immediately traceable.

Figure 12. Percentage of funded EOSS grants from each category, comparing manual curation versus automated approaches.²⁰

Conclusion

At the inception of this program in 2019, we set out to support the creators, maintainers, and contributors of essential open source software that provides key computational capabilities to researchers in the life sciences. Beyond funding, our goal was to understand the needs of these open source communities and help make their contributions to science *visible, fundable, and recognized*.

²⁰ Grants included are from cycles 1-5; EOSS-D&I was not included. Manual categories were assigned and curated by members of the CZI Open Science Program and represent only a single category per grant; percentages are available in [Table 2](#). The automated approach is detailed in [Application Corpus Analysis / Domain Categorization](#) and assigned multiple categories per grant.

Attendees gather for a group picture at the CZI Accelerating Open Science in Latin America workshop in Buenos Aires, Argentina in 2023.

Five years into the EOSS program, the community of open source leaders it supports offers an extraordinary opportunity to understand how open source powers science at large, and how to shape the science funding landscape to recognize its unique needs. While the impact of these projects and the communities behind them extends well beyond the data and stories we've compiled in this report, we hope this report can serve as both a resource and a stepping stone toward building a more sustainable future for key computational resources that power science.

For maintainers: a funder's ability to support your work is only as strong as the stories you share. Telling these stories is not trivial, given the media's bias for novelty and scientific breakthroughs, but allocating effort to compile quantitative and qualitative data on how your project advances science is one of the most important things you can do to enable policymakers and funders to support your work.

For institutions and funders: open source software is a [unique kind of scientific output](#) that, unlike other research products, requires ongoing care, funding, and dedicated resources to thrive and function. At the same time, investing in broadly adopted open source software is a force

multiplier that can unlock entire scientific communities. Organizations like the Research Software Alliance, your institution's open source program office, and national-level Research Software Engineer organizations can be your allies in coordinating these efforts.

For users of research software: the best thing you can do to support the computational tools you use daily in your work is to [cite](#) and acknowledge them in your published outputs in the same way you cite papers.

For science of science researchers: the study of how software is transforming science is still in its infancy compared to decades of bibliometrics research based on citation data. While there is no single data source for characterizing how open source is transforming science, new research to shed light on this question is essential for funders, institutions and maintainers themselves to advocate for its support.

We hope this report inspires more groups to partner and collaborate to build a stronger foundation for the open source ecosystem that powers science.

Acknowledgments

Completing a report with such a broad scope required monumental effort on the part of many individuals across CZI. Huge thanks to the following individuals for compiling, validating, and sharing data used in this report, and for their feedback and contributions, including: Natalie Ward and Esteban Parker (Open Science); Patricia Flores, Samantha Yammine, Yzabelle Dela Cruz, Giulia Notari, and Sabine Middlemass (Brand and Communications); Donghui Li, Sunil Mohan, Michaela Torkar (and Curation team), and Ana-Maria Istrate (Science Technology); Julia Klebanov, Sara Mahjoub, and Mikala Caton (Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning); Ivory Dean (Diversity in Science); Nina Cardoza and Meagan Mnich (Science Grant Operations); Wyatt Robarts, Erica Speights, Paul Kim (Legal and Grants). We also want to acknowledge our program advisors, who helped us refine the design of the program over the course of five funding cycles, as well as all the EOSS reviewers who helped CZI distill nearly 200 funded proposals from over 2,000 applications. Finally, we are immensely grateful to all grantees in the EOSS community, not just for embodying how investing in open source can transform science at large, but also for sharing their unique perspectives and impact stories that helped us compile this report.

Appendix A: Definitions

Table A1. Glossary of terms used in this report.

Depending on the nature of the question being addressed, data may be presented that represents different ways of subsetting EOSS-funded work (grants and software projects).

Term	Definition
Developer/Maintainer	An individual who engages in code creation or maintenance for a software project. While these roles may be distinct for some software projects, we use them synonymously because they are functionally similar in the context of our discussion.
EOSS	Essential Open Source Software for Science, a competitive funding program led by the CZI Open Science Program.
EOSS Cycle	A round or occurrence of funding, for which applications are solicited via RFA, reviewed, and recommended for funding. A number after EOSS indicates the cycle (1-5).
EOSS-D&I	Run concurrently with EOSS-4, this supplemental grant program was open to EOSS grantees from cycles 1-3 to support activities related to diversity and inclusion in EOSS projects.
EOSS grant	A proposal submitted to an EOSS RFA and selected for funding. Sometimes also called “funded proposal” or “grant project.” A single EOSS grant may support development for multiple scientific open source software projects. Each grant is considered a separate body of work in this report, regardless of whether the software project or PI had been funded previously.
EOSS grantees	PIs (principal investigators) and key personnel (named in the grant as a major contributor) of EOSS grants.
EOSS Software Project (EOSS project)	An open source software project for which an EOSS grant focuses software development effort. A single EOSS grant may support development for multiple scientific OSS projects. A software project may be funded multiple times, in different cycles of EOSS.
Open Source Software (OSS)	Open source software, software with source code that anyone can inspect, modify, and enhance (link)

Scientific Open Source Software (Scientific OSS)

A subset of OSS used primarily for scientific research; source code, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows, and executables that are produced with the explicit intention of being used by others ([link](#))

Table A2. Details of proposal categories used to describe applications.

Foundational categories represent applications useful across research areas; Domain-specific categories are designed to address certain areas within biomedical research.

Foundational:	
Data management and workflows	Data formats and storage, dataset transformation, workflow automation, platform features and software used by other systems; often back-end tools
Machine learning and data analysis	Statistical analysis, modeling/simulation, numerical computing; often end-user tools
Visualization	Creating charts/graphs, interactive visualization for data exploration and analysis
Domain-Specific:	
Bioinformatics	Analysis of genomics-adjacent data (e.g., metabolomics), packages uniting genomics with other types of data, libraries that support computational back-ends required by bioinformatic analyses
Cell Biology	Management and analysis of data at the cellular level, including single-cell biology
Clinical Research	Managing and analyzing electronic health records and other data related to diagnosis and treatment of human disease
Genomics	DNA and RNA-based data analysis
Imaging	Acquisition and analysis of imaging data, such as microscopy or MRI
Infectious Disease	Epidemiology (including genomic), disease tracking and simulation
Neuroscience	Neuronal and brain assessment, behavior tracking and analysis, neurodegenerative disease
Structural Biology	Identifying molecular structure and how molecules interact

Appendix B: Data Analysis

This appendix contains information about the data and analyses presented in this report, with data tables available in the associated data package with descriptive README. As a team focused on open science, we are committed to reproducibility, transparency, and data sharing. In this appendix and the associated data package, we endeavor to balance our commitment to openness with a need to protect the privacy of applicants and grantees. This is especially relevant for data sources that were not originally collected for the purpose of long-term analysis or public dissemination. Each subheading below represents a different data source, presented in the order in which they appear in the report; see [Figure 3](#) for a diagram showing relationships among data sources.

Relevant Links to Online Resources

The following links on CZI's website provide publicly announced information about the program:

- [Essential Open Source Software for Science program page](#): See bottom of page for links to stories about EOSS.
- [EOSS-funded proposals list](#): Title, summary, PI, key personnel, and software projects (also available in data package).
- [EOSS RFA](#): For the most recent cycle, includes information about what is required for proposals.

Application Corpus Analysis

Results from the Application Corpus Analysis are used in sections 1 (Applicant needs identification) and 6 (Domain categorization). Needs and categories assigned to anonymized proposals from application of models are available in the data package. Models and associated data are not available for public sharing because of the CZI privacy policy associated with submitted applications.

This project used text-based language models to extract additional learnings from all EOSS proposals from full applications in cycles 1-5 (e.g., the application corpus). Applications for EOSS-D&I were excluded as the proposals did not include relevant data to assess. There were two main areas of analysis for which natural language processing was applied:

1. Applicant needs identification
2. Domain categorization

Applicant Needs Identification

The first goal for the Application Corpus Analysis was to identify what scientific open source projects requested EOSS funding to support. Only data from the Work Plan field of EOSS applications were used to assess applicant needs. The Curation team from CZI Science Technology Research assisted in obtaining training data for models. Each sentence from full EOSS-5 applications were labeled with one or more need categories (Technical, Documentation, Community, Training, defined as in [Table 3](#)). Five additional categories (DEI impact, Presentation, Manuscript, Mentor/Mentee, Governance) were tested. These latter categories were eventually collapsed into Community for the final analysis due to low individual model quality.

The final models used for this analysis accumulated categories assigned to all sentences, meaning modeling was based on the entire text of the Work plan. A pre-trained BERT-like model (`allenai/longformer-base-4096`) was used to model text at the sentence level, as this model was able to handle the longer text lengths of the Work Plans. Tuning the decision threshold did not generally affect the performance of the final models ([Table B1](#)). The trained models were applied to applications across all cycles except the D&I supplements, which did not contain appropriate data for modeling.

Table B1. Sample performance scores for models predicting applicant needs (threshold of 0.35).

Metric	Documentation	Technical	Community	Training
precision	0.735	0.957	0.917	0.815
recall	0.893	1.000	0.943	0.917
f1_score	0.806	0.978	0.930	0.863
support	28	44	35	24
support_pct	61%	96%	76%	52%
pred_positives	34	46	36	27
pred_true_positives	25	44	33	22
pred_false_positives	9	2	3	5
pred_false_negatives	3	0	2	2

Domain Categorization

The second goal for the Application Corpus Analysis was to identify biological or analytical categories into which each EOSS application can be assigned. Each application was assigned a main/primary category by the CZI Open Science team as a part of the review process; categories are defined in [Table A2](#).

Training data were obtained from manually applying the two most relevant categories to each of 343 applications from EOSS-5. Four text fields from applications were used in training the model: Title, Summary, Landscape analysis, and Value to biomedical users. A model was created for each category using whichever was better scoring between a logistic regression or linear support vector machine algorithm, both of which were independent classifiers ([Table B2](#)).

Table B2: Performance scores for each category, comparing linear regression and linear support vector machine algorithm.

The best scoring model is indicated with an asterisk (*) next to the F1 score.

		Linear regression			Linear support vector machine		
Category	Sample number	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
Bioinformatics	98	0.544	0.610	0.575*	0.542	0.499	0.518
Cell Biology	35	0.622	0.845	0.701*	0.583	0.911	0.694
Clinical Research	56	0.545	0.558	0.545	0.578	0.646	0.606*
Data Management and Workflows	123	0.656	0.696	0.673	0.760	0.680	0.7188
Genomics	46	0.785	0.792	0.778*	0.571	0.838	0.678
Imaging	87	0.765	0.800	0.780	0.731	0.885	0.799*
Infectious Disease	36	0.805	0.731	0.731*	0.595	0.812	0.668
Machine Learning and Data Analysis	111	0.611	0.582	0.586*	0.470	0.706	0.562
Neuroscience	42	0.820	0.685	0.746	0.751	0.796	0.770*
Structural Biology	20	0.463	0.708	0.558	0.571	0.917	0.683*
Visualization	32	0.723	0.589	0.629*	0.586	0.563	0.564

After assigning categories using each automated model, proposals were labeled with zero to four categories (average = 2.23). Seven proposals did not have a category assigned; each of these had been previously identified as ineligible and/or not competitive for funding. The accuracy of automated category assignment was assessed by comparing the main/primary category previously assigned by CZI staff with the automated categorization assigned by models. Average accuracy across all eleven categories was 86%; the breakdown of accuracy by category is available in [Table B3](#). The automated approach underestimated the number of proposals in one category, Structural Biology, likely because that category had the fewest number of applications in the training set, and this sample did not adequately characterize the variation in language used in such applications. Results from other categories, however, suggest that the manual, single-category approach dramatically underestimates the number of EOSS grants relevant to particular fields of research.

Table B3. Accuracy of automated methods for assigning categories to proposals from EOSS cycles 1-5.

Accuracy is defined as the proportion of proposals for which automated methods labeled a proposal with the main category previously assigned to the proposal via manual curation.

Category	Accuracy
Bioinformatics	92%
Cell Biology	88%
Clinical Research	89%
Data Management and Workflows	95%
Genomics	75%
Imaging	84%
Infectious Disease	100%
Machine Learning and Data Analysis	75%
Neuroscience	100%
Structural Biology	62%
Visualization	82%

Needs Assessment Survey

Data from the Needs Assessment Survey is used in [Section 1](#). Anonymized responses to ranking questions are available in the data package; text-based responses to open-ended questions are summarized in the report above but are not included in the data package.

In August 2021, the CZI Open Science Program launched an informal needs assessment to identify opportunities to support maintainers and contributors to open source research software. We identified 19 key themes in scientific open source development and created a survey to assess their relative importance to funded software projects. In the survey, respondents were asked to rank each topic as “urgently needed”, “good but not essential”, or “not interested” in terms of what could benefit their project's core contributors.

EOSS PIs from cycles 1-4 were asked to respond and share with their key personnel, and we also asked other programs in CZI Science to share the survey with grantees engaged in open source development. Data was collected through November 2021. This was not intended to be a complete and comprehensive evaluation of the EOSS community or OSS in general, but rather a way to get rapid feedback on top-priority needs for grantee capacity building. We received a total of 51 responses from 34 project PIs, 15 key personnel, 1 advisor and 1 writer/organizer, representing 36+ software projects.

Grantee Output Analysis

Data from the Grantee Output Analysis is used in sections 2-6. Output tags assigned to anonymized proposals are available in the data package. Specific examples from reports are not included unless there is already a publicly available announcement available (e.g., blog post published by software project).

The Grantee Output Analysis was intended to characterize the deliverables produced by EOSS grantees as a result of their funding from CZI. The primary source of outputs were grantee interim and final reports, with additional outputs extracted from the 1) [Grantee Impact Survey](#) and 2) notes from CZI staff following regular check-ins with grantees. The grantee reports were processed in collaboration with the Curation team from CZI Science Technology Research. For all 265 annual reports received prior to the publication of this report, each output was extracted and labeled with one or more tags. Tags were compiled such that each grant is labeled describing the nature of the deliverables and/or the type of impacts produced by the grant. Additionally, quotations from this data source were used in cases where permission was provided by the author. Quotations may have been edited for brevity and clarity.

Output tags include all labels described in [Table 4](#), as well as the following tags describing types of impact:

- **Code of Conduct (CoC):** adoption of a CoC for a software project for the first time, implementing a new version of a CoC, or developing processes and practices for socializing and enforcing an existing CoC.
- **Collaboration:** interactions with another software project, including (but not limited to) enabling interoperability, synchronizing roadmaps, and submitting/reviewing code. Further detail on types of collaboration is available in [Section 4.2](#).
- **DEI:** activities related to increasing participation of individuals historically underrepresented in open source, both as developers and users of software, including (but not limited to) women, black/indigenous/people of color, individuals from LMICs. [Table 7](#) describes specific tags applied to further subdivide DEI impacts.

Grantee Impact Survey

Data from the Grantee Impact Survey is used in sections [3](#), [5](#) and [6](#). Anonymized responses to Likert-scale questions are available in the data package; text-based responses to open-ended questions are summarized and/or quoted in the report above but are not included in the data package.

The Grantee Impact Survey was specifically designed to obtain data for this report. This was not an anonymous survey, as we wanted to collect data on outputs and attribute to the relevant funded project. The survey included questions asking grantees about the importance of funding on project DEI, the uptake and use of the project software in biomedical research, and effects on primary project maintainers. Likert-scale questions asked for an answer along a range of importance (e.g., Not at all important, Somewhat important, Moderately important, Very important, Extremely important), and also solicited open-ended responses for respondents to share examples and/or explanations. The survey was open for a month in August 2023. PIs from cycles 1-5 were invited to respond, with 96 individuals representing 84+ software projects answering part or all of the survey.

Aggregated Application Data

Aggregated Application Data is used in sections [4](#) and [5](#). All anonymized, aggregated data available for sharing are represented in the associated figures; no additional data is included in the data package.

Software Development Practices

These data are shown in [Figure 8](#). Questions asked in applications related to software development practices are available in [Table 6](#). For some questions, projects not reporting a practice in their work may have answered “No” or “Not applicable.” It was optional to include a link to the relevant materials (e.g., the Code of Conduct on the project website, or the issue tracker on GitHub).

PI Demographics

These data are shown in [Figure 10](#).

- **Geographic location:** Data are presented for EOSS cycles 1-5. Cycles 2-5 used PI’s country of residence to identify geography. Country of residence was not solicited for cycle 1, so location of the PI’s organizational affiliation was used instead. Geographic locations were assigned a region using classification from the [World Bank](#), including: East Asia and Pacific, Europe and Central America, Latin America and Caribbean, Middle East and North Africa, North America, South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa. Not all regions are represented in the data from this report.
- **Gender:** Data are presented for EOSS cycles 1-5. Women, Non-Binary, and Third Gender were all available as separate options in the original application question; these collapsed to a single group to avoid categories with fewer than 5 individuals, as per CZI data sharing guidelines.
- **Race:** Data are presented here for EOSS cycles 4 and 5; equivalent data are unavailable to share for cycles 1-3. Three main categories are presented:
 1. White: a person having origins in Europe, or otherwise identifies with this category
 2. “Not reported”, which aggregates the following answers: Not reported, Prefer to describe myself, Prefer not to state. The exact options available varied across cycles.
 3. “Asian, Middle Eastern or North African, Hispanic or Latinx, Two or More Races, Black and/or African American, Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander, American Indian or Alaska Native” which aggregates the following answers. These categories were collapsed to a single group for the purposes of visualization and to avoid categories with fewer than 5 individuals, as per CZI data sharing guidelines:
 - Asian: a person having origins in the Far East, Southeast Asian, the Indian Subcontinent; this does not include Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
 - Middle Eastern or North African: a person having origins in or who maintain an affiliation to the Middle East or North African regions

- Hispanic or Latinx: a person having origins in Central and/or South America, Puerto Rico, and/or Cuba (this answer was updated to include Mexico in the description with EOSS-5).
- Black and/or African American: Afro-Caribbean, African American, Black and from an African nation, or a person who otherwise identifies with this category
- Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Two or more races: a person who identifies with more than one of the other categories

CZ Software Mentions

CZ Software Mentions data is used in [section 6](#). All data presented for EOSS projects from the updated dataset is available in the data package.

These data represent informal (e.g., not formally cited) mentions of scientific software in biomedical literature. The original dataset and description of its derivation are available in the following sources:

- Istrate, Ana-Maria et al. (2022). CZ Software Mentions: A large dataset of software mentions in the biomedical literature [Dataset]. Dryad. <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.6wwwpzgn2c>
- Istrate, Ana-Maria et al. (2022). A large dataset of software mentions in the biomedical literature. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.00693>

The data presented in this report are from an updated dataset with articles published through March 2024. However, data/metadata availability for late 2023 is incomplete for some publication sources, so only mentions through 2022 are shown in figures. Software projects included in this analysis represent those named in funded proposals. A visualization of mentions for all 186 software projects funded.

Figure B1. Software mentions by year of all 186 EOSS-funded software projects.

Data shown are from 2013 and 2016-2023.

Appendix C: EOSS Request for Information (RFA)

Although information about EOSS is currently available on the [CZI website](#), language for the [Opportunity](#) and [Selection Process](#) from EOSS-6 (the most recent cycle as of the time of writing) is included below for ease of reference.

Opportunity

Overview

Open source software is critical to modern scientific research, advancing biology and medicine while providing reproducibility and transparency. Hundreds of software packages, libraries, and applications have become essential tools for research — so much so that many researchers could not continue their work without them. Despite its importance, even the most widely-used research software often lacks dedicated funding for maintenance, growth, development, and community engagement. Also, those who work on such software often lack credit and recognition.

In an effort to support open source software for science, the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI), the Wellcome Trust (Wellcome), and The Kavli Foundation (Kavli) (“The Funders”) seek letters of intent to apply for funding for software projects that are essential to biomedical research. Ideal applications will have previously demonstrated impact, currently show potential for continued improvement, and expect to deliver added value to the biomedical research community through the proposed activities.

The Funders have partnered on this request for applications because of our shared commitment to supporting software critical to biomedical research. Although the process will use CZI infrastructure (e.g., application portal), The Funders are equal partners in this call. All applications will be considered by all funders. Selected proposals will be funded by either CZI, Wellcome, or Kavli, and the decision of which funder funds what will be made based on the corpus of selected proposals, their domain, and their alignment with funder goals. The decisions on which Funder supports a proposal will be made after evaluation and selection of the full proposals. Funders will provide requirements and information for the successful applicant at the time of award notification. All grants, regardless of funder, will be for two years and can be used to fund a variety of eligible activities, as listed in the Use of Funds section below.

Note this is a two step application process: an initial Letter of Intent (LOI), which will be followed by invitations to a select number of applicants to submit a Full Application.

With this program, we aim to provide software projects with resources to support their tools and the communities behind them. Whether it’s hiring an additional developer, improving documentation, addressing usability, improving compatibility, onboarding contributors, or convening a community, we hope our support can help make the computational foundations of biological research more usable and robust.

For this Request For Applications, we seek to support software tools across a broad range of biomedical fields, including (but not limited to)

- Imaging
- Single-Cell Biology
- Neuroscience
- Bioinformatics
- Genomics
- Structural Biology

- Clinical Biology
- Infectious Disease
- Data Visualization
- Data Analysis, Machine Learning, and AI
- Data Management and Workflows

Scope

Applications for two broad categories of open source software projects will be considered in scope:

- Domain-specific software for analyzing, visualizing, and otherwise working with the specific data types that arise in biomedical science. Software will be considered out of scope if it primarily serves domains outside biomedical science without strong evidence of adoption in biomedicine.
- Foundational tools and infrastructure that enable a wide variety of downstream software across several domains of science and computational research. While foundational tools will be considered in scope for this program, they must have demonstrated impact on some area(s) of biomedical research.

We strongly encourage proposals requesting funding for multiple related software projects (as in this [example](#)). For examples of open source projects CZI has previously funded through the EOSS program, we encourage you to check the list of [proposals awarded in the previous cycles](#) and CZI's [blog posts](#).

Examples of projects that are less likely to be successful in this RFA:

- A project in its earlier stages that is not used extensively or known beyond the creator(s);
- A project that is focused on improving or supporting a database or knowledge base that has few community contributions or low adoption in the biomedical community;
- A project that is widely successful and adopted but has little or no applications to biomedicine; and
- A proposal for a research project to mine, publish, or analyze research results rather than a project that will support the biomedical research process itself.

Use of funds

Applications can request funding between \$50,000 USD and \$200,000 USD total costs per year for two years (inclusive of up to 15% for indirect/overhead costs) for an overall amount requested between \$100,000 USD and \$400,000 USD total costs for the two-year duration of the grant. Proposals will not need to provide a detailed budget or justification at the LOI stage. At the full proposal stage, budgets will be required and evaluated for appropriateness relative to the scope of work proposed.

Acceptable use of funds includes, but is not limited to:

- Salary support for staff (full-time, part-time, or contract): developers, contributors, technical writers, community managers, product managers, project managers, user experience researchers, community educators, or other roles that directly support the software project(s);
- Hackathons, sprints, outreach, or other forms of community engagement and support for community participation;
- Operational needs such as cloud computing, storage, networking, or continuous integration services; and
- Support for work that bridges software projects or ecosystems, including better coordination across software projects that are similar, dependent on one another, or frequently used together.

Selection Process

We adhere to values of people, technology, collaboration and open science in both proposal selection and evaluation of progress.

Applications will be evaluated for their existing impact, the quality of the open source software project(s) involved, the feasibility of the proposal, the expected value of the funded work to the biomedical community, and their diversity, equity, and inclusion statement. Each of these categories will be assessed through quantitative and qualitative factors. Relevant materials will be provided by the applicants and obtained by The Funders from publicly available sources where possible (e.g., GitHub or other public code repositories).

For those applicants asked to submit a Full Application, additional quantitative metrics on software projects will be requested. Independent expert review will be solicited, and final decisions will be made by CZI, Wellcome and Kavli staff in consultation with our expert advisors.

Impact will assess the importance of the open source software project(s) involved in the proposal to science and the open source ecosystem, in alignment with CZI's mission to support the science and technology that will make it possible to cure, prevent, or manage all diseases by the end of the century. Reviewers will evaluate:

- Demonstrated scientific impact and adoption of the software project, with a particular focus on its use in biomedicine
- The role of the software project in the scientific open source ecosystem

Alongside qualitative materials, expert evaluation may use metrics such as:

- Number of users and recent growth
- Adoption within relevant communities
- Number of citations or mentions of the software project in scientific literature
- Number of potential contributors and diversity of the organizations they represent
- Number of past contributions to related software projects in the relevant software stack (pushing changes upstream to dependencies, receiving changes from other nearby software projects)

Quality will assess the maturity of the software project(s), its compliance with best practices in open source development, and the existence of a healthy and diverse contributor community. It will again be assessed qualitatively and quantitatively. Reviewers will evaluate:

- Composition and leadership of team
- Governance structure of the software project
- Software project communications and community engagement
- Existence, clarity, and recency of software project roadmap
- Clarity of process for external contributions
- Evidence of external contributions from outside of the core developer team (in the form of code, bugs/issue reports, documentation, etc.)
- Availability of tutorials and examples

- Quality and comprehensiveness of documentation.

Alongside qualitative materials, evaluation may leverage metrics such as:

- Frequency and growth trajectory of commits over time
- Size and make-up of current developer team
- Frequency of external contributions
- Number of open issues, and rate of issues both opened and closed
- Time between opening and closing of pull requests.

Feasibility will assess the plan of work described in the proposal and whether it can be accomplished given the requested budget and key personnel involved. Reviewers will evaluate the following based on qualitative materials:

- Specificity and clarity of plan of work to be accomplished
- Proposed use of funds (relative to plan of work)
- Likelihood of the work being accomplished
- Plan for tracking and validating progress against goals
- Degree of unmet need given existing resources
- Future plans for sustaining or maintaining the work funded by the grant.

In addition to the above criteria, reviewers will evaluate the value to the biomedical community of the proposed work, in particular:

- How the output of the proposal will advance project(s) adoption among biomedical researchers or produce value to their work
- Biomedical user needs that are unmet by the software project(s) in their current state and that will be addressed through the proposal
- Any improvement or integration with other tools that will improve the adoption, usability, functionality, extensibility, ease of use, or performance of the project in the context of the biomedical research community.

Lastly, all applicants invited to submit a Full Application must include in their proposal a Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) statement, describing (1) any efforts the software project(s) named in this proposal have undertaken to increase diversity, equity, and inclusion with respect to their contributors and audience; and (2) the results of such efforts, if applicable. This statement will be reviewed alongside the above criteria. Please see [examples](#) of DEI statements from successful proposals funded in previous cycles.

There is no expectation of any specific number of awards for this RFA program, however this grant program operates within a budget which will inform the overall number of awards that are recommended for funding. The Funders reserve the right to not recommend the funding of any applications.

Reporting and Progress

Annual reports, including a summary of the project progress that may be made publicly available, will be required from successful grantees to ensure that progress is on track toward the deliverables described in the proposal. Measures of progress will also include additional indicators on the growth and uptake of the software project, as obtained from code repositories, issue trackers, package distribution systems, community forums, mailing lists, etc.